

Exploring Plasticity Rules in the Biologically Realistic Simulation of Neuronal Cultures

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Introduction

- Neuronal cell cultures connectivity develops over time.
- Neuronal plasticity might describe these changes
- I added plasticity rules to the state of the art simulations
- This simulation may complement and inform real experiments

In silico setup and model

- Biologically plausible neuronal growth
- N=1000 neurons, 800 excitatory, 200 inhibitory
- Sparse connectivity matrix (2% of cells filled)

Fig. 1 Two neurons in the biologically plausible simulation of initial axonal growth. Source: Orlandi et al. 2013

Fig. 2 The resulting initial neuronal network. Dots are the neurons; edges are the axons (directionality not shown)

- Izhikevich model of neuronal activity
- Spike-time dependent plasticity, synaptic depression and synaptic scaling as plasticity rules

$$v' = 0.04v^2 + 5v + 140 - u + I$$

$$u' = a(bv - u)$$

Eq. 1 Izhikevich model equations. I : input current (A), u , v : state variables, a , b : parameters

$$D(t+1) = \frac{1 - D(t)}{\tau_D}$$

$$I_j^{inc}(t) = \eta_j(t) + \sum_i W_{ji} \cdot D_i(t)$$

Eq. 2 Synaptic depression equations. I : outgoing current (A), η : Gaussian random noise, W : connection weight, D : dyn. vector
Spike-time dependent plasticity was implemented analogously

$$\Delta W_{ij} = \frac{(s_j(0) - s_j(t))}{\tau_{SS} \cdot N_{conn}}$$

Eq. 3 Synaptic scaling. s_j : sum of the column j in W , τ_{SS} - synaptic scaling constant (determined in simulations *in silico*)

Simulation execution

Simulation was run using MATLAB™ engine on an HPC cluster. Runtime was a big concern even in a simplistic setting described.

Fig. 3 Raster plot of the simulation spiking activity, 10 seconds runtime.

Experimental setup

- *In vitro* experiment: receptor silencing on a 13 day *in vitro* rat embryonic primary neuronal cultures
- Hypothesis: „real“ culture rewires synaptic channels to maintain firing rate

Fig. 4 Raster plot of the firing activity of the real neuronal culture. DIV: days *in vitro*. CNQX, APV, BIC: biological silencing agents, restricting the neurons firing activity

Experimental application

- Model „silencing“: reduce excitatory neuron outgoing weights by factor of $\gamma=0.2$
- Plasticity mechanisms model „rewiring“ *in silico*

Fig. 6 Simulation of a real synapse silencing experiment. 1 – before silencing, 2 – simulation of CNQX addition, 3 – simulation of CNQX removal, 4-6 – activity „overshoots“

Conclusion & Outlook

- Developed a plasticity-aware simulation of a 2D culture. This can be used to investigate 2D network dynamics *in silico*.

Fig. 7 Inter burst intervals in spiking activity of simulation runs of 5 minutes with different plasticity mechanisms employed.

- Checked a hypothesis for a real experiment within the simulation - it can be supported by *in silico* evidence
- *In silico* – *in vitro* correspondence: network „overshoots“ after silencing
- Further adjustments in time scales, computational optimization, metrics of *In silico* – *in vitro* correspondence needed

Fig. 8 Velocity of burst propagation in the cultures. Ticks 1-4: real observations, ticks 5-6: simulation (Sim). The velocity was computed using the Fradera lab's in-house software

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